

Air Printer: Using Digital Fabrication to Inspire Resilient Futures of Universities

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Abstract

This year is the National Tsing Hua University's anniversary, our FAB LAB FBI team used Digital Fabrication to develop a "Light Stick" to celebrate Tsing Hua's birthday. We held the activity "How Tsing Hua Can You Be?" Every student could hold a Light Stick to design a slogan representing Tsing Hua's spirit. This system as an "Air Printer" that can text or patterns in the air. The Light Stick utilizes the Persistence of Vision, combining Internet of Things modules and LED light strips, among other components. Through the Air Printer workshop, students will learn about circuit assembly, structural assembly, and how to capture and perform. We believe the performance can be considered a form of "Social Media Post," where everyone uses the Light Stick to post their ideas in the air. We also used the Self-Determination Theory and the Pleasure Theory to conduct a questionnaire analysis of these processes. The result of the analysis, this activity could achieve intrinsic and extrinsic motivational outcomes for the students. We hope this Air Printer model can create a creative "Mass Learning" and encourage students to utilize Digital Fabrication methods and interdisciplinary knowledge to integrate local spirit and culture.

Keywords

Air Printer, Digital Fabrication, IoT, Social Media Post, 3D-Printer, Arduino, Persistence of Vision, Self-determination, Pleasure Framework.

1 Introduction

Singing the "Happy Birthday Song" is a common way of celebrating birthdays at National Tsing Hua University. April 29, 2023, on the 112th anniversary of the school's founding, everyone on campus is considering how to celebrate the school's anniversary. In previous years, most people celebrated this anniversary event through performances, sports competitions, and carnivals. However, this year, our FAB LAB FBI team utilized Digital Fabrication to develop an "Air Printer," allowing students to print birthday wishes or designs mid-air to celebrate National Tsing Hua University's birthday. FAB LAB FBI is located in the Research Center for Technology and Art, National Tsing Hua University. We used the Digital Fabrication method for designing the "Light Stick." Everyone holds a Light Stick on campus and prints out the blessing slogan at National Tsing Hua University. These slogans are filled with creative humor, enthusiasm, critical thinking, and youthful ideas. They inspire National Tsing Hua University to reflect on embracing young people and create resilient futures together.

The core technology of the Air Printer uses Persistence of Vision (POV) technology, which converts text or image into a light point signal and prints it through the air with a Light Stick. It is recorded by the shooting method of the long-exposure camera APP. The user can use the smartphone's Bluetooth transmission control APP to toggle different texts or images. We initiated the "Air Printer – How Tsing Hua Can You Be?" celebration project during the school celebration. First, students must spend a week learning digital fabrication to make the Light Stick. After that, students should consider "How Tsing Hua Can You Be ?" Everyone should reflect deeply on what Tsing Hua's mind is, what Tsing Hua's culture is, and what Tsing

Hua's impression is. This activity serves as a celebration of National Tsing Hua University's birthday. On the other hand, it serves as a means to “inspire” students to reflect on the spirit and culture of the university. We believe that this group performance can be considered a form of “Social Media Post,” where everyone uses the Light Stick to post their ideas in the air.

The “Self-Determination Theory (SDT)” was proposed by Professor Edward L. Deci from the United States and Professor Richard M. Ryan from Australia in 1985 [1]. The SDT emphasizes the exploration of intrinsic motivation in humans, which is driven by inner beliefs that are positive and self-sustaining. This theory has inspired us to design the “How Tsing Hua Can You Be?” activity, where students can use the Light Stick to design slogans or patterns that they believe represent the spirit of Tsing Hua University [2]. We are exploring whether this can inspire students to feel more deeply about the campus. The Pleasure Theory [3], proposed by Canadian anthropologist Lionel Tiger in 1992, explores whether people can feel pleasure after using a new product. We used this theory to explore whether Light Sticks can produce pleasurable feelings during learning and participation. We organized Air Printer workshops to allow students to participate in “Digital Fabrication Collective Creation.” Through the performance arrangement of school celebration activities, students can participate in “Mass Learning” and encourage and appreciate each other. Corresponding to the Self-Determination Theory and the Pleasure Theory, the results of the entire workshop and school celebration activities are positive and motivating.

2 Related Work

In the past, there have been various types of applications for Light Stick, with most of them utilizing the visual persistence effect and controlling LED light pixels to create the illumination and extinction of pixel points. The human visual system requires about 1/16th of a second to perceive the lingering afterimage of visual persistence, and the duration of continuous visibility is only around 0.1 to 0.4 seconds [4]. Using a camera to capture the visual persistence effect of LED light flashes allows for a theoretically infinite duration of Light Stick illumination and extinction. Therefore, such applications often involve using a camera with LED Light Stick. In 2012, ARS Electronic Futurelab created a performance artwork called “Spaxels” that combined drones with LED devices to create 3D Light Art using the visual persistence technique [5]. This groundbreaking work explored new forms of visual persistence about spatial dimensions, as shown in Figure 1 (left). On the other hand, the Russian artwork team TUNDRA utilized high-speed rotating visual persistence devices to create a series of LED visual persistence artworks called “Inexistence” [6]. By combining spatial and dynamic variations of LEDs, they presented unique visual art forms in terms of space and time, as shown in Figure 1 (right).

Figure 1: (Left) the artwork of “Spaxels,” and (Right) “Inexistence”

In similar past projects, there have also been approaches that involve hands-on making. For example, the “Dot Star” project developed by the American company Adafruit is based on the CircuitPython development board [7]. The Dot Star project by Adafruit allows program control of 32 LEDs and utilizes 3D printing to create the handle and supporting components. When users swing the LED device while using long-exposure photography, the LED light points are captured and stored. The Dot Star project's product is similar to our Light Stick but smaller and has fixed content that cannot be changed. In contrast, our Air Printer allows for dynamic content switching anytime.

In recent years, wireless communication technology has made significant advancements. The leaps forward in technologies such as Bluetooth, 4G, 5G mobile networks, LoRa, and Wi-Fi 6 with high bandwidth and low latency have made the vision of the “Internet of Everything” (IoE) increasingly realistic [8]. The convenience of the internet has become an integral part of our lives. These technologies have expanded the perspectives and possibilities of experiencing artworks. It has opened up new avenues for appreciating art and exploring artistic expressions. In 2013, Arnall, Knutsen, and Martinussen from the Oslo School of Architecture and Design in Norway created the art installation “Immaterial: Light painting Wi-Fi” [9]. They utilized Wi-Fi signal sensors to convert the detected Wi-Fi signal strength in the environment into a white light LED Light Stick composed of individual LEDs. The number of LED light points displayed would increase with stronger Wi-Fi signals in the space and decrease with weaker signals. Arnall et al. captured the presentation of these LED light points using long-exposure photography, recording the process with a camera. They created a “Light Enclosure” in the environment, as shown in Figure 2, producing a unique humanistic and artistic atmosphere.

Figure 2: “Immaterial: Light painting Wi-Fi” artwork create a Light Enclosure

“Self-Determination Theory (SDT)” was proposed by Edward L. Deci from the United States and Rich M. Ryan from Australia in 1985 [1]. The theory primarily explores how individuals strive to fulfill three innate psychological needs: competence, relatedness, and autonomy. These needs, intrinsic to human nature, contribute to optimal development and progress for individuals. SDT has wide-ranging research and application in various fields. For instance, in Human-Computer Interaction (HCI), SDT has been used to explore the intrinsic and extrinsic motivations in game design [10]. In STEM education curriculum design, SDT has been applied to understand how teachers, as curriculum designers, can create a positive learning environment for students [11]. Within Makerspace communities or educational settings, SDT has been utilized to investigate sustainability, examining the intrinsic and extrinsic motivational aspects of makers' support for the continued operation of Makerspaces [12]. In 2018, we utilized IoT technology and traditional Taiwanese bamboo weaving craftsmanship to develop the “ESPSAS” IoT platform [13]. We applied this platform at Taipei Municipal Nanmen Elementary School in Taipei, Taiwan, allowing elementary school students to unleash their maker spirit by creating windmill flower objects. During the day, the windmill flowers would spin in the wind, and at night, they would transform into colourful lanterns, as shown in Figure 3. The entire activity involves using a collective networked action art approach to transform the campus and revitalize the community [14]. This demonstrates that the creative design of the activity can foster intrinsic motivation and a sense of identification within the community toward the environment. In this research, we also aim to explore whether our designed Air Printer workshop can stimulate students' extrinsic motivation for learning. When students contemplate creative slogans for the Air Printer, does it also evoke an intrinsic motivation among their peers to reflect on the spirit and culture of National Tsing Hua University actively?

Figure 3: The ESPSAS platform workshop design combining IoT and windmill flowers

In addition, Canadian anthropologist Lionel Tiger published “The Pursuit of Pleasure” in 1992, exploring the pleasure derived from novelty and new experiences [3]. He proposed four categories of pleasure: physio-pleasure, socio-pleasure, psycho-pleasure, and ideo-pleasure. These categories encompass pleasure's physiological, social, psychological, and intellectual aspects. In the analysis and application of pleasure theory, Huang, Y., Liao, C., and Hsu, S. discussed the analytical methods of pleasure theory in their 2021 HCII paper, which can demonstrate how a new experiential or innovative sensation can bring psychological and physiological pleasure [15]. We also want to investigate whether students' participation in the Air Printer workshop can enhance their interest and sense of pleasure and even help overcome the shortcomings of limited social interactions due to the past pandemic situation.

3 Air Printer Development

The imaging principle of the Air Printer is based on the use of visual persistence technology. We have combined IoT (Internet of Things) modules with LED light strips and other electronic components to cater the device. It is capable of dynamically switching between different slogans or content. In order to achieve this goal, we have developed the Air Printer system and designed the Air Printer workshop to allow students to learn circuit assembly, structural assembly, and how to capture and operate the Light Stick. In order to sustain the visual persistence effect in the space, we have designed the structure of the Light Stick to extend up to 2 meters. It has Bluetooth connectivity, allowing wireless control through an Android smartphone. Through custom “Command Packets,” we can dynamically switch the SD card's content between text and images. In order to achieve this goal, we have developed the Air Printer system and designed the Air Printer workshop to allow students to learn circuit assembly, structural assembly, and how to capture and operate the Light Stick. Additionally, the primary display method of the Light Stick relies on an LED light strip. The length of this light strip is approximately 1.88 meters, consisting of 200 LED pixels. Each LED pixel is capable of displaying RGB colors. Through this LED display method, using long-exposure software on a smartphone, it is possible to capture and record the effect of the Air Printer.

The essential component in the Air Printer system is the Light Stick device structure, which includes a 2 meters long acrylic tube, an aluminum extrusion for LED slots, LED light strips, Arduino modules, and more. We combined standard Digital Fabrication tools such as laser cutters, 3D printers, circular saws, welding tools, and more for production and development. We have planned an Air Printer workshop where students can actively participate in assembling and operating each component. The main tasks that students will engage in during the workshop include:

3. Assembly of the main control board: Includes soldering electronic components onto the board, soldering IC sockets and assembling Arduino, pin headers, and SD card module, and connecting battery wires and LED strip signal wires, among others.
4. Assembly of the device structure: Includes the assembly of the 3D printed structure fixed with acrylic, the assembly of the LED strip, the assembly of the aluminum extrusion LED Light track, the assembly of the signal wires, and the assembly of the 3D printed cover.

5. Software installation: Includes installing and operating the slogan conversion software, Bluetooth transmission app, and long-exposure app.

3.1 Air Printer Assembly for Main Control Board

The main control board is the core component of the Light Stick, which includes the USB Power Adapter, LED Strip Adapter, IoT Bluetooth Module, Switch, and SD Card Module, as shown in Figure 4. The assembly and soldering steps for the main control board are as follows:

1. To assemble the Printed Circuit Board (PCB): Begin by soldering the relevant electronic components onto the circuit board. Then, solder the necessary signal wires onto the circuit board.
2. Assemble the Arduino module to control the LED strip display: Sold a 28-pin IC socket onto the circuit board and trim any excess pins. Then, insert the Arduino module into the IC socket.
3. Solder the header pins onto the SD card module: The SD card module is responsible for accessing the text or image data files and transferring them to the Arduino controller. We use an SD card module that already has pins soldered onto it. Therefore, we must sell the header pins onto the module for proper connection.
4. Assemble the USB power cable: This step involves connecting the USB power adapter to the main control board to provide power to the circuit. The USB power cable allows for the activation and deactivation of the system.

Figure 4: The assembly diagram of the main control board

3.2 Air Printer Assembly for Device Structure

We have designed several 3D printed components using Digital Fabrication methods, as shown in Figure 5. The installation steps are as follows:

1. First, assemble the aluminum extrusion LED light strip holder. This part consists of two sets of components and 3D-printed snap-fit connectors, as shown in Figure 5(a).
2. Insert the assembled LED light strip holder into the LED light strip. Use strong double-sided adhesive to securely attach the head and tail ends of the LED light strip to the holder, as shown in Figure 5(b).
3. Insert the LED light strip holder from one side of the acrylic tube, as shown in Figure 5(c).
4. And then, connect the signal wires from the main control circuit board to the LED light strip in the device structure.
5. Finally, cover the ends of the light stick with the 3D printed end caps, as shown in Figure 5(d).

Figure 5: Assembled using a Digital Fabrication Light Stick structure

3.3 Air Printer Software Install and Application

The circuit and structural assembly is complete. Three applications are involved in software control:

- The long-exposure app
- The software for converting text or images into light point signals
- The mobile app for Bluetooth transmission control

In this Light Stick control system, we utilize wireless IoT transmission to achieve the goal of the Air Printer, which is to "print" any text or image in the air. The core technology of the Air Printer relies on the persistence of vision, transforming text or images into light point signals that are "printed" in the air using the light stick. The process is recorded through long-exposure photography with the assistance of the app. Users can use Bluetooth transmission on their mobile phones to switch between different text or images. Figure 6 shows the process photos of students participating in the Air Printer workshop, including circuit assembly, device structure assembly, and software installation.

Figure 6: Student participation in the work process

4 Air Printer Performance

During the school festival, we organized the "Air Printer - How Tsing Hua Can You Be?" activity. Students spent a week assembling the Light Sticks. Afterward, they were required to reflect on "How Tsing Hua." They delved deeply into what the Tsing Hua spirit, Tsing Hua culture, and Tsing Hua impression mean.

Ultimately, they designed their thoughts into a “slogan” and used the Air Printer - Light Sticks to perform and “print” their slogans on the campus during the school festival.

4.1 Team Division

During the school festival performance, three students formed a group. One student was responsible for using the Bluetooth control app on their phone to switch between different slogans. Another student was in charge of capturing the performance through long-exposure photography using their phone. The third student was the performer with the Light Stick. They stood about 3 to 5 meters from the camera's perspective and slowly walked from left to right, creating a “Light Painting” effect recorded during the photography process. The entire activity sparked students' high interest and participation in Digital Fabrication and allowed the school to appreciate the creative use of the Air Printer to celebrate the school festival. Most importantly, the process of thinking and designing different slogans stimulated everyone to reflect on the spirit and culture of the school and even critically contemplate the university's resilient future.

4.2 Performance Results

Students participated in the performance interpretation during the school's 4th-month anniversary celebration. The slogans designed by the students were creative and reflected the thoughts of contemporary young people. These slogans were closely related to the National Tsing Hua University anniversary and held historical significance for the older Tsing Hua alums. After we posted these Air Printer creations on Facebook, they formed a social media post. They received feedback from National Tsing Hua University alums, sparking many memories of their past study experiences at National Tsing Hua University. Throughout the Air Printer interpretation process, the students also shared their experiences on social media, expressing their imagination and creativity to a broader audience. Within the team collaboration, students were assigned different roles. Some operated mobile phones, some were responsible for photography, and others carried the Light Sticks and performed. This process tested the students' teamwork, and we discovered that the better the teamwork, the more brilliant and diverse the creative ideas. It also indirectly showcased their positive and proactive learning attitude in this activity.

Here are some of the slogans from the various groups:

1. “Build the Future_Tsing Hua Construction Site” - Aspiring for a future Tsing Hua campus filled with a vibrant atmosphere of humanities and arts through recent construction projects such as the campus art gallery, music hall, and literature center.
2. “The Clear Night Touches the Heart, Stars of Tsing Hua and Autumn Moon” - Expressing the dedication of Tsinghua students who often stay up late into the night, studying, completing assignments, and preparing for exams while engaging in introspective thinking.
3. “Refreshing and Extraordinary, Gathering of Tsinghua's Excellence” - Expressing the exceptional abilities of Tsinghua students, soaring above the clouds and showcasing their talents. Tsinghua University is a gathering place for extraordinary individuals.
4. “Organize the Traffic, Only Tsing Hua” - Satirically referring to Tsinghua's ambition to surpass the neighboring school (whose name sounds like “traffic”) in various aspects.
5. “D986BC34” - This is the hexadecimal code representing the geographic coordinates of Tsinghua University (as shown in Figure 7(c)).
6. “Later going for McDonald's or 7-11?” - This slogan reflects the dilemma faced by students every day, whether to choose McDonald's or 7-11(convenience store), highlighting the limited dining options available on campus (as shown in Figure 7(d)).

In addition to the creative slogans created by the 14 student groups, faculty members, and alums, they actively participated in designing slogans representing the spirit of National Tsing Hua University. The Vice President suggested “Actions Speak Louder than Words” as Tsing Hua's spirit, which originated from a

statement by the late President Mei Yi-chi, emphasizing the importance of practicality (as shown in Figure 7(a)). The 50th-anniversary alumni proposed "Tsinghua's Call, Eternal Inheritance" to symbolize the continuation of historical slogans. The faculty suggested that Tsinghua is a "Paradise for Mavericks" full of academic freedom (as shown in Figure 7(b)).

Figure 7: The results of a slogan of Air Printer

5 Conclusions and Future Works

Regarding the effectiveness of the Air Printer, we conducted a questionnaire survey based on the Self-Determination Theory and the Pleasure Theory. The survey was administered to 42 students participating in the workshop and the campus celebration event, and we collected 22 valid questionnaires. The results can be found in Appendix A.

According to the questionnaire results, our Air Printer workshop was able to motivate students' extrinsic motivation for learning. It also stimulated students' intrinsic motivation, encouraging them to actively reflect on the spirit and culture of National Tsing Hua University.

1. **External motivation:** According to the questionnaire results from Q1, Q2, Q4, Q5, Q7, and Q9, 51.52% strongly agreed and 42.42% agreed. Therefore, 93.94% of the students believe that the Air Printer workshop can stimulate their external motivation.
2. **Internal motivation:** According to the questionnaire results from Q3, Q4, Q5, Q6, Q7, and Q8, 55.3% strongly agreed and 41.67% agreed. Therefore, 96.97% of the students believe the Air Printer workshop can stimulate their internal motivation.

Can Social Media Posts allow students to experience the pleasure and novelty of interdisciplinary learning?

3. **Physio-pleasure:** From the results of Q5 and Q8, 50% strongly agree, and 43.18% agree. Therefore, 93.18% of students find that the Air Printer workshop can give them physiological pleasure. We hope this Air Printer model can create a creative form of crowd activity and encourage students to utilize digital fabrication methods and interdisciplinary knowledge to integrate local spirits and culture, thus inspiring their diverse creativity.
4. **Psycho-pleasure:** From the results of Q4 and Q6, 61.36% strongly agree, and 36.36% agree. Therefore, 97.77% of students expect that the Air Printer model can fulfill their needs for interdisciplinary learning and teamwork, and they can gain new knowledge, experiences, and a sense of freshness from it.
5. **Socio-pleasure:** From the results of Q2 and Q7, 47.73% strongly agree, and 45.45% agree. Therefore, 93.18% of students believe that performing with the Air Printer, sharing school celebration slogans, and creative ideas with others can generate a sense of pleasure.
6. **Ideo-pleasure:** From the results of Q3 and Q5, 40.91% strongly agree, and 54.55% agree. Therefore, 95.45% of students participating in the Air Printer workshop experience a profound sense of

ideational pleasure when exploring school celebration slogans and engaging in hands-on assembly activities as they create and accomplish tasks.

The research findings confirm that the "How Tsing Hua Can You Be?" slogan design in the Air Printer project can generate the motivational effects proposed in Deci's Self-Determination Theory. Additionally, students' participation in the light stick assembly process can evoke the "physio-pleasure" and "psycho-pleasure" described by Tiger. Furthermore, the Social Media Post featuring the light stick performances can provide students with "socio-pleasure" and "ideo-pleasure" in line with Tiger's Pleasure Theory. Analysis of the results shows that 94.89% of students experienced various forms of pleasure, indicating a strong agreement regarding the enjoyment derived from the Air Printer project.

The Light Stick developed through the Air Printer method, which allows printing text or patterns in space, can have various extended applications in the future, such as event advertising, stage performances, creative teaching, and more. The designed device can also become a new type of "Mass Activity" or "Collective Creation," bringing together interdisciplinary knowledge and creative ideas to imagine the future and inspire students' diverse creativity.

In addition, we have brought this light stick to rural areas in Taiwan, such as Shakeng Elementary School and Lao Da Fen Leisure Farm, for similar activity applications. We have engaged elementary school teachers and students, elderly farmers, and the public in using the light stick device through the Air Printer method. This enables us to promote STEAM interdisciplinary education and agricultural regeneration as a social service in rural areas. We have transformed the achievements of Air Printer into various creative activities, inspiring more concern for the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). By focusing on quality education, sustainable urban and rural development, and reducing inequality, we aim to expand the benefits and sustainability of Air Printer.

This year at FAB 2023, we have applied to host a workshop titled "Air Printer - How FabLab Can You Be?" where participants can learn to create Light Sticks and use them to print their version of "How FabLab Can You Be?" in the beautiful mountain scenery of Bhutan. Let us combine and use Digital Fabrication to inspire more creativity and critical thinking, leading to positive societal change and creating a resilient future.

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Appendix A

Questions	Correspondence Theory
<p>Q1: Do you find it interesting to see everyone's Light Stick results sharing in the unit of Air Printer?</p> <p>Results: 31.82% strongly agree, 59.09% agree, 9.09% disagree, 0% absolutely disagree</p>	SDT: Extrinsic motivation
<p>Q2: Regarding the design part of "How Tsing Hua Can You Be?", did it inspire you to think about the impression of Tsing Hua or the spirit of Tsing Hua?</p> <p>Results: 22.73% strongly agree, 63.64% agree, 2.89% disagree, 0% absolutely disagree</p>	SDT: Extrinsic motivation Pleasure Theory: Socio-pleasure
<p>Q3: Regarding the design of the "Slogan for School Celebration", do you agree that "exploring and thinking is also a kind of creativity"?</p> <p>Results: 36.36% strongly agree, 63.64% agree, 0% disagree, 0% absolutely disagree</p>	SDT: Intrinsic motivation Pleasure Theory: Ideo-pleasure
<p>Q4: Do you feel more creative and imaginative in the design of "Light Stick Color Creative Edition"?</p> <p>Results: 81.82% strongly agree, 18.18% agree, 0% disagree, 0% absolutely disagree</p>	SDT: Intrinsic motivation, Extrinsic motivation Pleasure Theory: Psycho-pleasure
<p>Q5: Regarding the practical unit of "Air Printer", do you think it is easy to control the assembly, operation and interpretation?</p> <p>Results: 45.45% strongly agree, 45.45% agree, 9.10% disagree, 0% absolutely disagree</p>	SDT: Intrinsic motivation, Extrinsic motivation Pleasure Theory: Physio-pleasure, Ideo-pleasure
<p>Q6: Regarding the practical unit of "Air Printer", do you think it can give full play to the spirit of "cross-domain" and "teamwork"?</p> <p>Results: 40.91% strongly agree, 54.55% agree, 4.55% disagree, 0% absolutely disagree</p>	SDT: Intrinsic motivation Pleasure Theory: Psycho-pleasure
<p>Q7: Do you think the "creative sharing" among classmates is important? Share ideas that inspire each other.</p> <p>Results: 72.73% strongly agree, 27.27% agree, 0% disagree, 0% absolutely disagree</p>	SDT: Intrinsic motivation, Extrinsic motivation Pleasure Theory: Socio-pleasure
<p>Q8: In the practical unit of "Air Printer", did you learn new knowledge, experience, or feel fresh?</p> <p>Results: 54.55% strongly agree, 40.91% agree, 4.55% disagree, 0% absolutely disagree</p>	SDT: Intrinsic motivation Pleasure Theory: Physio-pleasure
<p>Q9: Regarding the practical unit of "Air Printer", the practical unit of technology and art appreciation in the next semester, do you suggest that this unit should still be available?</p> <p>Results: 40.91% strongly agree, 54.55% agree, 4.55% disagree, 0% absolutely disagree</p>	SDT: Extrinsic motivation
<p>Q10: Regarding the "Air Printer" practice unit, do you have any suggestions? (Short answer)</p>	SDT: Intrinsic motivation